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Research Review

The phylotypic brain of vertebrates, from neural tube closure to brain diversification

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Abstract

Background

The *phylotypic* or intermediate stages are thought to be the most evolutionary conserved stages throughout embryonic development. The contrast with divergent early and later stages derived in the concept of the evo-devo hourglass model. Nonetheless, this developmental constraint has been studied as a whole embryo process, not at organ level. In this review, we explore brain development to assess the existence of an equivalent brain developmental hourglass. In the specific case of vertebrates, we propose to split the brain developmental stages into: 1) *Early*: Neurulation, when the neural tube arises after gastrulation. 2) *Intermediate*: Brain patterning and segmentation, when the neuromere identities are established. 3) *Late*: Neurogenesis and maturation, the stages when the neurons acquire their functionality. Moreover, we extend this analysis to chordates and deuterostomes brain development to unravel the evolutionary origin of this evo-devo constraint.

Summary

Based on the existing literature, we hypothesise that a major conservation of the *phylotypic brain* might be due to the pleiotropy of the inductive regulatory networks, which are predominantly expressed at this stage. In turn, earlier stages such as neurulation are rather mechanical processes, whose regulatory networks seem to adapt to environment or maternal geometries. The later stages are also controlled by inductive regulatory networks, but their effector genes are mostly tissue specific and functional, allowing diverse developmental programs to generate current brain diversity. Nonetheless, all stages of the hourglass are highly interconnected: divergent neurulation must have a vertebrate shared end-product to reproduce the vertebrate phylotypic brain, and the boundaries and transcription factor code established during the highly conserved patterning will set the bauplan for the specialised and diversified adult brain.

Key Messages

The vertebrate brain is conserved at phylotypic stages, but the highly conserved mechanisms that occur during these brain mid-development stages (Inducing Regulatory Networks) are also present during other stages. Oppositely, other processes as cell interactions and functional neuronal genes are more diverse and majoritarian in early and late stages of development, respectively. These phenomena create an hourglass of transcriptomic diversity during embryonic development and evolution, with a really conserved bottleneck that set the bauplan for the adult brain around the phylotypic stage.

Introduction

There is no doubt about the essential role of the nervous system in adaptive behaviours, but little is known about how evolution yielded the responsible striking differences across current species brains. Development is the major source of evolutionary divergence, so comparing the evolutionary variations of the nervous system development might shed light to the mechanism responsible for current brain diversity [1]. Unfortunately, there is still not enough knowledge about the extent of conservation of brain development, not even among chordates. Which modifications in development allowed the appearance of the current myriad of brains? Are there developmental stages specially conserved throughout all chordates? Which are the reasons behind these evolutionary trends?

Based on von Baer's laws [2; translated and reviewed in 3] and Haeckel's studies [4; reviewed in 5], it is agreed that evolutionary conservation varies across developmental stages. These influential researchers suggested a causal relationship between developmental and evolutionary events, proposing the highest conservation in what they identified as the earliest stages of development within a given phylum. These early stages are now referred to as *phylotypic* stages, defining the general body plan and features of a phylum. However, due to the technical limitations of Baer's and Haeckel's time, earlier stages such as morula and gastrula were not fully understood [Abzhanov, 2013], except in a few species, and their divergence was unknown. Subsequent discoveries of embryological differences in the earliest stages, beyond the phylotypic, led to the current model known as the hourglass of developmental variation [6; 7] (**Fig. 1A**). This model elucidates the timing and causes of differential conservation around the phylotypic stages.

According to this model, the earliest stages morula and gastrula, are quite diverse even at the class level, like in mammals. This diversity is thought to relate to maternal genes and structures, including feeding tissues such as the trophoblast or the yolk. These adult maternal elements highly influence the early developmental processes and make it very variable among closely related species [8]. But after gastrulation and neurulation, the intermediate or phylotypic stages display a deeply conserved morphology in the embryos. At these stages, organogenesis takes place and regional specification of the different brain segments or cell-types occur [9]. A high percentage of these patterning and segmentation genes are conserved in vertebrates and chordates [10; 11]. Finally, during the later stages, cells gradually acquire their adult functions, so this late embryo seems to get morphologically and transcriptomically as divergent as the adult form. As such, the hourglass model details that the most diverse stages are at the top and bottom -early and late development-, whereas there is an evolutionary constraint or bottleneck for diversity in the mid-embryonic stages (**Fig. 1A**). Even though

the hourglass model is supposed to apply to all phyla, even for plants [12], chordates is the only one which seems to have been experimentally tested [13].

Nonetheless, there is still debate about the special conservation of mid-developmental stages across evolution. Authors like Levin et al. (2016) [14] claim that early and late stages are more conserved across all phyla, but intermediate stages are more conserved within. Other authors like Richardson (1995) [15] argue that the differences in developmental timing hamper the possibility of finding a phylotypic stage, being this concept a rather abstract term than a specific developmental time point.

Beyond the embryonic level, several authors hint at the existence of a phylotypic conservation for each individual organ [16]. Although this approach could solve problems in organ heterochronicity, the hourglass concept has been hardly investigated in any organ, and the existence of an hourglass of diversity in brain development remains unexplored. The existence of a shared early brain in all chordates or vertebrate species would not only be key to establish evolutionary homologies between adult brain cell types, but also to decipher the mechanisms that preserve organogenesis mechanisms and drove the evolutionary divergence across the phylum in earlier and later developmental stages.

Figure 1.

In this review, we explore brain developmental stages to assess the existence of a brain developmental hourglass equivalent to that of the whole embryo. In the specific case of vertebrates, we propose to split the brain developmental stages into: 1) *Early*: Neurulation, when the neural tube arises following gastrulation. 2) *Intermediate*: Brain patterning and segmentation, when the neuromere identities are established. 3) *Late*: Neurogenesis and maturation, the stages when the neurons acquire their functionality.

For this purpose, we have revised the emergence of the neural tube, how it is patterned and segmented, and which mechanisms trigger neurogenesis and successive developmental divergence across the Chordata phylum and its sister groups (Hemichordata and Echinodermata, **Fig. 1B**). The evolutionary comparisons of these three key developmental points have led us to endorse the existence of an equivalent brain hourglass, where there is a chordate phylotypic brain with a highly conserved patterning machinery. This phylotypic brain may not only establish the conserved plan for building a vertebrate brain, but may also involve the limits of variation of brain structure.

1. Neurulation - The neural tube emergence

All chordates display a hollow neural tube along the midline of its body, a feature that contrasts with other phylum nervous systems, mainly ganglionic. This centralised hollow nervous system is thought to have provided chordates with advanced olfaction and taste reception (the hollow neural tube could have allowed the diffusion of food particles, enhancing better sense perception), as well as improved hydraulic and skeletal properties [17]. Developmentally, the neural tube derives from the invagination and folding of the flat bidimensional neuroectoderm into a hollow neural tube. This process is known as *neurulation*, and names the stages after gastrulation up to the pharyngula.

During the last decades, studies in many fishes, amphibians, birds and mammals have described the communalities and differences of neural tube emergence [18; 19; 20]. However, there seems to be a different degree of conservation between two interconnected processes: the **neural induction** and its **mechanical morphogenesis**.

Highly conserved morphogens such as *WNTs*, *BMPs*, *FGFs* and regional transcription factors (e.g. *HOX*) are widely known to control development in an equivalent manner across chordates, and even across deuterostomes [21; 22; 23]. Probably for this reason, gene regulatory networks (GRNs) have historically gravitated around these master genes in charge of specifying or controlling cell fates. However, we differentiate several GRN sets according to their ultimate function within cells. Downstream of fate masters must be the functional action of effector gene networks regulating morphogenesis and mechanical processes, such as cell cycle, cell division, adhesion, polarisation, cell migration, cavitation, extension, branching, and many others. Steventon et al., (2021) [8] defined this latter set of genes as cell regulatory networks (CRNs), controlling the mechanical life of the cell. And we are naming as *inductive regulatory networks* (from now on, IRNs) to those regional sets of genes governing induction and cell fate. Although both CRNs and IRNs are included in the global GRNs, we could hypothesize, first, that IRNs are hierarchically regulating CRNs and, second, that the sets evolved disparately. However, there is not yet enough knowledge to distinguish how these divergent CRNs molecularly interact and evolve with the conserved neural IRNs.

Stages like gastrulation and neurulation display divergent morphogenesis processes, a divergence that relates to maternal influence and environment [19]. However, all these processes end with the same final result of the neural tube neuroepithelium. The contrast of this early divergence with the high constraint brain bauplan forced the evolution of CRNs to adapt cell migration and interaction to the evolving geometry, but managing to reach the final conserved neural tube and brain bauplan of IRNs. To unravel the hypothetical diversity below the phylotypic bottleneck, we are going to break down neurulation into neural induction (governed by IRNs) and mechanical morphogenesis (ruled by CRNs).

Their description, similarities and differences across vertebrates will be key to identify causal relations for their likely independent evolution that led to this canalization phenomena.

Neural induction

Although in this section we will describe the commonalities among vertebrates [24; 8], many of these elements are also shared by chordates [25; 26] and even deuterostomes [27]. Early in development, β -*CATENIN*, a common pre-localized maternal determinant, triggers the medial appearance of equivalent Spemann-Mangold organisers (SMO) (**Fig. 2**, in orange) [28; translated in 29]. This first patterning determines the initial axes of the embryo, which will lead to gastrulation and the appearance of ectoderm, mesoderm and endoderm (**Fig. 2**; blue, yellow and magenta). At gastrulation, ventral regions are dominated by *BMPs* and *WNTs* morphogens, while dorsal left cells are protected by their inhibitors -*CHORDIN*, *NOGGIN*, *FOLLISTATIN* - produced by the SMO (**Fig. 2A**) [30]. These cardinal signals will be crucial for all subsequent stages and processes.

These dorsal cells are the future neuroectoderm as well as the dorsal mesoderm (prechordal plate, pharyngeal endomesoderm) (**Fig. 2C**). The latter will ingress through the blastopore and elongate beneath the neuroectoderm, giving rise to the antero-posterior patterning. As the prechordal plate and initial notochord advances anteriorly, the blastopore regresses till being located at the posterior end (prospective anus). Additionally, the amniote anterior visceral endoderm (AVE) is also defining the most anterior region as the prechordal plate [24].

Both prechordal plate and visceral endoderm in amniotes protect the most anterior neural plate through morphogens such as *CERBERUS*, *FRZB*, *DICKKOPF* and *IGFs* that block the *BMPs* and *WNTs* signalling to drive *OTX2* expression on the above neuroectoderm, which determines the anterior brain identity (secondary prosencephalon and mesencephalon) (**Fig. 2B'**) [31].

Nonetheless, not only is it needed the absence or blockage of *BMPs* and *WNTs* for the ectoderm to become neural (default hypothesis) [32; 33], other signals as *FGFs* are also essential to determine the neuroectodermal fate and control its proliferation [34; 35]. Moreover, *WNTs*, *FGFs* and *RA* gradients will posteriorize the tube, being highly expressed at the trunk level and decreasing at anterior, head levels. In the absence of these morphogens, the neural tissue will become anterior [32; 33].

Along with this described antero-posterior patterning occurs the dorso-ventral patterning, simultaneously. While the neuroectoderm is extended anteriorly, its invagination starts to take place. This morphogenic process allows a physical segregation of the inner neuroectoderm (future ventral)

to the lateral neuroectoderm (future dorsal). Thus, being exposed to different morphogen actors as *BMPs* from the non-neural ectoderm (dorsal); and *SHH* secreted mainly by the notochord (ventral) (**Fig. 2B''**) [36; 37]. These dorsoventral cues also drive the expression of a set of regional transcription factors such as *PAX3*, *CDX2* and *ZIC2*, which also control neural tube closure [38; 39].

Figure 2.

Nonetheless, the medial / optic domain of the most anterior neural plate follows a different behaviour. The *SHH* secreted from the basal hypothalamic plate inhibits optic nature in the medial foremost brain, and at the same time the hypothalamic plate rostral migration bisects the highly proliferative optic domains into two [40]. Thus, both IRNs and CRNs combine to locate the optic vesicles laterally to the neurulating secondary prosencephalon.

To summarise, these IRNs can be identified across vertebrates despite their early embryonic different geometries (**Fig. 2B**), and maintain an extremely conserved fate mapping role. However, without the existence of tightly controlled mechanical neurulation and gastrulation, the morphogens would not induce the proper cells and we would not obtain the patterned neural tube that defines all vertebrate organogenesis [41].

Mechanical morphogenesis

The elongation of the neuroectoderm as well as its invagination are both mechanical processes. However, the forces involved in proliferation, migration and other CRNs are highly evolutionarily diverse due to gastrulation geometries and extraembryonic structures (**Fig. 2B**, in grey). These highly diverse processes are still orchestrated by the above-described conserved morphogens and regional transcription factors. How have CRNs evolved independently from IRNs? Which are the driving forces for this evolutionary divergence?

As soon as the neuroectoderm is induced, the whole gastrula expands longitudinally and simultaneously, the neuroectoderm is narrowed into the engrossed neural folds by apicobasal thickening [19]. Mechanically, this is achieved by furrowing and folding. The first one is mainly governed by microtubules, which are responsible for cell elongation; the second one by microfilaments, which force the apical constriction of cells [42]. This process is known as *convergent extension* and it is mainly regulated by the non-canonical *WNT*/Planar Cell Polarity (PCP) pathway [43], which is shared by most vertebrates [44; 19]. PCP pathway also appears to control the bending of the neural folds at its lateral extremes, creating the neural groove [45].

Despite these commonalities, there are several differences between amniotes and anamniotes. Firstly, amniotes display a pseudostratified epithelium [46; 47; 48; 49; 50; 51] (**Fig. 2D**). This unique columnar epithelium leads to the interkinetic nuclear migration, where the cells are located along the apicobasal axis based on its cell cycle: basal, S-phase; apical, mitosis. This distribution and the proportion throughout the neural plate favours the above-described neurulation [52; 53; 54].

In contrast, the anamniotes' neural plate is a bilayered structure and during neurulation, the deep layer cells intercalate between the superficial layer ones to form a single-layered epithelium (*radial intercalation*) (**Fig. 2D-E**, early to late neurulation). As the edges of the neural folds are still far, there is a medial migration from lateral cells to complete the closure [55], even at the secondary prosencephalon [40]. This cell behaviour is extremely similar to the early mesenchymal properties of the neuroepithelium, but eventually it will lead to a more epithelial neural tube with apico-basal domains and tight junctions [56; 57; 58].

This mesenchymal-like behaviour has been largely misconceived as secondary neurulation in teleosts [59; 60; 48]. However, the fact that teleosts' neural keel is derived from the epithelial neural plate engrossment and invagination into a neural rod clearly determines it as primary [20].

Secondary neurulation occurs in posterior levels of the spinal cord, such as sacrae vertebrae. In these regions, the neural tube arises from the condensation of neuromesodermal progenitors that condensate into a solid cord that will eventually caveate to form a hollow tube [61]. Nonetheless, this feature is exclusive of vertebrates as invertebrate chordates as cephalochordates and tunicates only display primary neurulation, which is therefore considered to be ancestral to secondary [62; 63]. This innovation is another example of the evolutionary diversity before reaching the neural tube, whose patterning and segmentation is completely equivalent along the spinal cord [20].

This mesenchymal behaviour in anamniotes neural tube is possibly a non-homologous convergent phenomenon, as it is also present differently in other vertebrates. For instance, the lumen is also occluded at some levels of the spinal cord in chick and amphibians (primary neurulation) [55]. This is an example of the intra-species variability displayed in the neurulation along the neural tube, present also in mammals [64].

Another relevant difference happens at the completion of neurulation, which involves the fusion of non-neural ectoderm and neuroectoderm. The fusion of both tissues implies their remodelling [65] and is originated by protrusions amid the midline gap. These actin-rich protrusions can be either

lamellipodia and/or filopodia, being highly variable depending on the antero-posterior level and species [66].

The momentum in which this phenomenon occurs is also different between amniotes and anamniotes (**Fig. 2E**, late neurulation). While in amniotes the non-neural ectoderm plays an important role pushing both folds towards the midline [67], in anamniotes, non-neural ectoderm rapidly epibolies the neural plate, and thus, scarcely contributes to the neural tube closure. This independent epidermal closure could be driven by a selective pressure to limit the lumen exposure to the external environment, which is covered in amniotes by the amnion. Thus, the lack of this extrinsic force could explain the need of mesenchymal-like cell mechanisms to quickly drive neural closure [20].

Additional divergent phenomena are the closure sites and features. Even within the mammalian class, there are diverse closure points, ordering and timing [19]. Chicks display two points of closure initiation, at the level of the rhombencephalon-cervical boundary and at the future mesencephalon, both with bi-directional zipping between them [68]. Humans also display two closing sites, one also at the cervical/rhombencephalon boundary, but other located at the most rostral end of the secondary prosencephalon [69]. However, this is not a mammalian feature, as mice have an additional closing site at the secondary prosencephalon/mesencephalon boundary [70].

Last, but not least, it is important to highlight other essential factors whose impairment can derive in neurulation defects and are not well studied across vertebrate species: extracellular matrix components (*LAMININ*, *N-CADHERIN*), proteases (*PAR1*, *PAR2*) and proliferation regulators [19; 71; 72].

All in all, although the neurulation appears to have more conserved features than gastrulation, there are still major morphogenic differences, which might be revealing transcriptomic differences at the CRN level. However, the release from highly mechanical or geometrical forces after the neural tube closure, leaves the following, phylotypic stage of the brain mainly dominated by patterning IRNs: chemical inducers and regional identity transcription factors.

The evolutionary origin of the neural tube

The neural tube emergence is a hallmark of chordates and has definitely impacted their diversity in comparison with other Metazoa. However, there are many unanswered evolutionary questions: Which mechanisms lead to neural tube emergence in chordates? How the emergence of new CRNs interacted

with conserved IRNs? Is there any difference between chordate and vertebrate neurulation end-product?

Ambulacraria, the closest relatives of Chordates

Echinodermata and Hemichordata are chordate's sister groups, key to understand how the neural tube arose 500 million years ago. Chordate's differences with these outgroups may allow us to understand how an increase of *BMPs* signalling and *HH* (*SHH* in chordates) appearance could have led to the neuroectoderm internalisation.

Nonetheless, identifying an equivalent homologue nervous system to the chordates is hotly debated in the field. Although some authors consider the apical organ as the homologue for the chordate brain [73], there are still scenarios that hypothesize the ciliary band as homologue of the chordate CNS [74; 75; 76]. In this review, we will focus on the mechanisms that could have led to a tubular nervous system [77; 78], rather than the conservation of patterning GRNs [73].

Su et al. (2019) [78] hypothesize that an increased expression of *BMPs* would have led to an internalised CNS as in chordates, as ectopic overexpression led to neurogenesis suppression and ciliary band condensation in a ventral ectoderm [77; 78] (summarised in **Fig. 3A**). Moreover, their ectopic *BMP* led also to mouth's disappearance on the non-*BMPs* side. Thus, an internalised CNS would need a *BMP* compatible mouth, as it occurs in chordates (*BMP*-expressing side mouth) [79; 80; 81].

On the other hand, the later metamorphosed organisms and direct developer hemichordates do appear to already own the earliest example of tubular nervous system ([82]; summarised in **Fig. 3B**). At the middle region, there is a tubular structure opened anterior and posteriorly: the collar cord. This pseudo neural tube is formed by dorsal invagination without the formation of a neural folds or groove, but through midline cells which contain myofilaments [83]. This mechanism highly resembles chordate neurulation and suggest a potential ancestral mechanism to the chordate neural tube despite the lack of equivalent dorso-ventral patterning up to date [79].

However, there is not enough evidence to connect this primary neurulation with the *BMPs* overexpression effect in CNS internalisation of echinoderms and pre-metamorphosed larvae. The role of *BMPs* specifically at this middle region is unknown, but what it is described is the existence of a dual patterning gradient as in chordates. When neurulation occurs, the *BMPs* expression is located over the internalised ectoderm collar [79], as in chordates. On the ventral pole, *CHORDIN* and *HH* antagonise *BMPs* and create a dorso-ventral (D-V) gradient across the embryo [79; 82]. Moreover, the collar cord

seems to respond to *HH* (*PTN* receptor expression), which promotes neural tube morphogenesis in chordates [21].

BMPs seem to may have been important for CNS internalization; but in the ancestral hemichordate neural tube, the appearance of an antagonising ventral organiser as the stomochord could also be key for neural tube morphogenesis. The effect of chordin on early gastrulation and ciliary band appears to have been enhanced by the endodermal stomochord, which might have some evolutionary relationship with the meso-endodermal prechordal plate. All these findings point to the need of a dual morphogen gradient for the morphogenesis and patterning of the chordate neural tube.

Figure 3.

Chordates

The hollow neural tube is a hallmark of the chordate phylum, but the end product of neurulation is not exactly equivalent in all chordate groups. The most distant group (cephalochordates, also known as amphioxus) follows simple roll-up of the epithelial neural plate, with morphological specificities of its subphylum [83; 84]. However, in contrast with vertebrates, the neural tube remains open anteriorly, likely acting as a directional chemosensing system [17]. Furthermore, there is only a single frontal eye, distinctive feature against the paired vertebrate eyes [40]; and its mouth is thought to have derived from a lateral gill, differently from echinoderms, hemichordates and vertebrates [80]; summarised in **Fig. 3C**). These important differences suggest the existence of different vertebrate IRNs, besides the expected CRNs diversity.

On the other hand, urochordates or tunicates are the closest subphylum to vertebrate chordates. However, its neural tube is lost after metamorphosis, so only the larvae display the chordate features. As well as amphioxus, their neurulation is quite similar to vertebrates and it is well characterised [85; 86]. Moreover, the anterior neuropore is repurposed into the neurohypophyseal duct under the control of *PITX* IRN, which connects with the novel evaginated tunicate mouth anlagen [87] (**Fig. 3C**). In vertebrates, *PITX* is also involved in oral ectoderm development, via its upstream morphogen *NODAL*, which is also required for anterior neural tube closure [88]. As indicated in echinoderm gastrulation, its effector *NODAL* is involved in SMO determination, but it is also essential later in neural patterning of the ventral secondary prosencephalon [89]. Further experiments would be essential to decipher how *NODAL/PITX* define the most anterior secondary prosencephalon through neuropore closure.

Thus, it seems that tunicates share the secondary prosencephalon (see the following section) limits with vertebrates, likely displaying a more vertebrate-like patterning. The closure of the neural tube at the most anterior region brings the *BMP* signalling also anteriorly, probably modifying the primordial amphioxus fate map. However, there seem to be missing other vertebrate IRN innovations to add the paired eyes and the critical telencephalon and hypothalamus expansion, which will lead to the vertebrate brain general organization, referred as the brain *bauplan* for its similarities and relationship to the general body plan [90].

In conclusion, neurulation is a dual process with really conserved identities due to homologue IRNs, but divergent CRNs to adapt neurulation to the diverse extraembryonic structures and environment pressures. These IRNs (*BMP* and antagonists) appear to be essential for the neural tube morphogenesis even in the ancestral hemichordate collar cord. However, the anterior limits and IRNs of the neural tube have evolved till vertebrates (neuropore closure and *PITX* signalling). Consequently, it remains unknown how the later phylotypic brain cell types are influenced by this neurulation disparity in chordates or whether taxon innovations have originated despite the shared neural tube in vertebrates.

2. Patterning - The segmentation of the neural tube

Adult cell type identity is determined by the positional information given during development, specifically at this intermediate or phylotypic stage [91]. These IRNs pattern or induce a specific positional identity, with specific transcription factors governing a specific region (**Fig. 4A**) [92].

However, the extent of conservation of these IRNs is still under debate. While some argue that each phylum is thought to display a distinct combination of signalling pathways and transcription factors that confers a phylum-specific body plan [14], other authors claim that the regional transcription factors that define positional identities in all axes are highly conserved across bilaterians [93]. Nonetheless, there seems to be a consensus about the bilaterian conservation of *BMP* signalling [94] and anteroposterior IRNs (e.g., *OTX2*, *HOX*) [95], which seem to act as general body plan outliner, not exclusive of the neuroectoderm [21; 96].

On the other hand, the dorso-ventral patterning conservation is still dubious. The existence of diffuse red-nets with neither dorso-ventral patterning nor centralised nervous system, such as in hemichordates, hampers this possibility. For this reason, Martín-Durán et al, (2018) [96] consider analogous dorso-ventral patterning (e.g., *MSX2/NKX2-1/PAX6*) as a convergent phenomenon. Likely general body transcription factors that compartmentalised the whole embryo and later were co-opted convergently by both arthropods and chordates to stagger dorsoventrally the neuroectoderm.

However, others such as Arendt et al., (2015) believe that these dorso-ventral regulators were also controlling neuroectoderm in the bilaterian ancestor and attribute these exceptions to secondary losses.

Whatever case it may be, there seems clear that the brain bauplan of chordates must include an inverted *BMP* signalling with morphogen organisers to determine anteroposterior identities (anterior neural ridge, zona limitans intrathalamica, isthmus) and dorsoventral identities (notochord, floor plate, roof plate, epidermis). These combined CRNs and IRNs are characteristic of only chordates [21; 30; 11; 98] , defining its essential brain coordinates and cell types, but also delimiting its boundaries and early diversity.

As in the previous chapter, we will firstly describe those IRNs which are shared across vertebrates to finally compare this vertebrate outline with other sister chordates as urochordates and cephalochordates.

The developmental cell types of the early brain

The patterning of the vertebrate early brain starts during gastrulation and reaches its highest peak at the phylotypic or pharyngula stages, when organogenesis is coordinated by multiple organ secondary organisers. Nonetheless, these broader segments of this stage, hosting regional developmental cell types (**Fig. 4B**), will acquire more complex and specific sub-regional identity at later stages, in parallel with neurogenesis and other morphogenetic processes.

Nonetheless, these early developmental cell types and IRNs are considered highly enriched with conserved positional information that allows us to establish homologies in comparative neurobiology despite disparate adult function [90]. For this reason, this early brain is named as the *brain bauplan*, because these IRNs comprise the essential building blocks of the vertebrate brain.

In this section, we will review the molecular insights of the segments of the three main brain vesicles: rhombencephalon, the most posterior region; mesencephalon, the intermediate region; and prosencephalon, the most anterior region. Due to its high evolutionary conservation, we will only refer to original discoveries of gene regulators or organizers, rather than the vertebrate wide confirmation studies.

Rhombencephalon

The posterior mesoderm secretes signals such as *WNTs* and *RA* [99], but *WNT1* is the morphogen that determines the anterior border of the rhombencephalon (**Fig. 4C-D**)[100]. As explained before, the *OTX2* anterior domain is protected by the prechordal plate during neurulation [32], and this transcription factor represses the posterior prosencephalic master gene *GBX2* [100]. This division is known as the *isthmus* or mesencephalo-rhombencephalic boundary. After its induction, *WNT1* expression is restricted anteriorly and *FGF8* gains importance in the prosencephalic patterning posteriorly [101]. However, there are many markers which are common to the whole isthmus domain such as engrailed genes [102].

These anteroposterior chemical morphogens end up with the emergence of segment-specific homeobox (*HOX*) gene expression. This is a defining expression that happens in a temporal collinear manner: anterior segments appear earlier, along with the expression of the first *HOX* genes; posterior segments are generated later, together with the expression of late *HOX* genes [7]. Thus, *HOX* genes regulate the identity of the rhombencephalon neuromeres, called rhombomeres. But these regulators not only control the neural rhombencephalon, they also determine mesenchymal and epidermal tissues such as pharyngeal arches or the otic vesicle [103]. Moreover, there are specific transcription factors that control specific rhombomeres. For instance, *EGR2*, which specifies rhombomere (R)3 and R5 [104].

In addition, the early role of non-neural ectoderm and notochord -tissues that express *BMP* and *SHH* in opposite gradients- in dorso-ventral patterning is respectively later extended to the roof and floor plate of the neural tube. While the roof plate expresses *WNT* agonists as *RSPOs*, *BAMBI*, *WNT1* [105], the floor plate keeps expressing *SHH* controlled by *FOXAs* transcription factors [106].

The dorso-ventral gradient leads to a stratification of the rhombomeres with basal/ventral domains expressing *NKX2-2/NKX6-2*, among others, and alar/dorsal domains are characterised by *MSX2/ZIC2/PAX6* expression (**Fig. 4C-D**) [107]. The combination of both dorsoventral and anteroposterior transcription factors leads to a unique combinatorial code for each neuromere domain that will determine the developmental fate of cranial nerves and other brain structures. Many cranial nerves originate in the rhombencephalon, and the strong conservation of rhombomeric segmentation is highly related to the conservation of cranial nerves in vertebrates. In addition, most rhombomeric structures are essential for the life of the individual and convey severe consequences if impaired [108].

Mesencephalon

Together with the prosencephalon, the mesencephalon is governed by anterior *OTX2*, but how prosencephalon and mesencephalon are subdivided? As explained before, *WNT1* is expressed anteriorly to the isthmus, defining the mesencephalon region [109]. On the other hand, the prosencephalon receives specific anteriormost signals and the posterior prosencephalon (diencephalon) is controlled by *PAX6* [110]. This homeobox antagonises isthmic transcription factors such as *EN1/EN2/PAX2*, defining the mesencephalon between prosencephalon and isthmus (**Fig. 4B-D**) [111]. Although there is little information about how this happens, this early cross-repression must lead to the appearance of *MEIS2*, which will later govern mesencephalic boundaries [112]. The mesencephalon is thought to be divided into two anterior and posterior mesomeres, but some mesencephalic transcription factors as *MEIS1* and *DMBX1* are also expressed in the first neuromere of the diencephalic vesicle [113; 114].

Similarly to the rhombencephalon, the mesencephalon displays a roof plate and a floor plate fostered by the dorsal non-neural ectoderm and notochord respectively [105; 106]. Nonetheless, there is a different variety of agonists and/or regional regulatory elements. In the roof plate, *WNT1/WNT3* are now the major dorsalizing molecules [109; 115] with *ZIC2* and *PAX7* as the main dorsal TFs [116]; and on the other hand, the floor plate still produces *SHH* as main morphogen to induce the mesencephalon basal plate controlled by *NKX6-1*, but in this region *LMX1A* is also controlling floor plate identity [117]. This dorso-ventral staggering is essential for leading to the tectum/tegmentum division later on development [111].

Prosencephalon

As described before, *PAX6* is early induced in the anterior neural plate and it extends to the mesencephalon [111]. Likewise, the anterior neural ridge (ANR), which is the anterior-most organiser, is induced by the prechordal plate. In turn, the ANR expresses *FGF8* that induces the *SIX3* transcription factor [118]. *SIX3* expression covers up to the posterior prosencephalon, where the zona limitans intrathalamica will appear (**Fig. 4B-D**). Antagonistically, the notochord *SHH* induces the expression of *IRX3* from the notochord end in the posterior prosencephalon up to the isthmus [119]. Both *SIX3* and *IRX3* are mutually repressive and drive different effector genes even in presence of the same signals [30]. This cross-repression creates the main prosencephalic division: secondary prosencephalon (telencephalon and hypothalamus) and diencephalon.

Diencephalon

The posterior prosencephalon or diencephalon can be divided into three antero-posterior units termed prosomeres (P): the pretectum (P1), the thalamus (P2) and the prethalamus (P3). The floor plates of all prosomeres are controlled by the *PITX2* [120]. Together with *PITX1*, this IRN might be responsible for inducing the pituitary or acroterminal organizer in the rostral hypothalamus [88].

However, there is a clear distinction between P1/P2 and P3. The aforementioned *IRX3* only controls P1 and P2, posterior to the zona limitans intrathalamica [30]. The dorsal *WNT3* signalling induces thalamic transcription factors such as *TCF7L2* [121] and dorsally *GBX2*, only in prosomere 2 (**Fig. 4B-D**)[122]. Meanwhile, P1 seems to be influenced by isthmus morphogens such as *FGF8*, sharing midbrain markers like *MEIS1* and *DMBX1* [123].

On the other hand, the zona limitans intrathalamica arises at the rostral end of the notochord. Its cells act as a boundary and express *SHH* from the ventral to the dorsal regions of the neural tube. Thus, the isolated P3 is likely to be more influenced by rostral morphogens from the ANR, leading to expression of *LHX5* and *BARHL2* [124]. This P3 shares a transcriptomic profile similar to the hypothalamus, being considered as such by some authors [125]. The dorsal P3 highly expresses *WNT7A*, being highly connected to the telencephalic cortical hem [124]. However, these dorsal morphogens must induce more ventral regions governed by *OLIG2* [126].

Figure 4.

Secondary prosencephalon

The notochord exerts only a minor influence over the secondary prosencephalon, as it only slightly reaches the peduncular prosomere. Instead, the hypothalamus -derived from the secondary prosencephalon- is highly controlled by prechordal plate morphogens (*BMP7*, *WNT* antagonists, *SHH*) [127]. Early in development, the ANR creates a protective gradient of *WNT* antagonists, which derive in the expression of *SIX3* and *SIX6* (**Fig. 4C-D**) [128]. However, *WNT* morphogens play an important role in the later development of telencephalon. This combination of gradients will lead to a further subdivision of secondary prosencephalon dorso-ventral and antero-posteriorly [90].

The dorso-ventral axis is early established by the *NODAL* morphogens coming from the prechordal plate, which induce the expression of basal *NKX2-1* [129]. *NKX2-1* controls the ventral secondary prosencephalon, or hypothalamus, promoting the *SHH* expression [130]. In contrast, the dorsal secondary prosencephalon or telencephalon expresses first *GLI3*, a repressor of *SHH* pathway, and later *FOXP1* [131]. However, the hypothalamus also includes some nuclei that are not controlled by

NKX2-1, but by more alar transcription factors such as *OTP* and *FOXG1* [132; 133]. The absence of a clear combination of TFs in this intermediate area suggested that this region may not be hypothalamic, but derived from the optic recess region [134] or a telencephalo-optic-hypothalamic domain [133].

In addition to the *SHH* and *FGF* gradients, there is an extra *WNT* source coming from the cortical hem at the most dorso-posterior end of the telencephalon [131]. The *FGF* signalling will protect the ventral telencephalon, defining the *NKX2-1* and *GSH2* subpallial regions [128] and displacing the *PAX6* controlled territory to the dorsal telencephalon or pallium. Thus, *GSH2* will govern the ventral telencephalon or subpallium [131]. Later on development, the posteriorizing hem *WNTs* will lead to *EMX2* expression at the posterior end, leaving posterior pallium under *PAX6* control (**Fig. 4B-D**)[135].

As described in the first chapter, the optic vesicle evagination is a highly mechanical process where IRNs and CRNs combine. The optic vesicles arise from the most anterior neural plate, but are displaced laterally by the elongating hypothalamic neural plate [40]. This unique position will derive in the induction of specific transcription factors such as *RX* [136], which in combination with *SIX3* and *PAX6* will establish the boundaries with other prosencephalic segments by *EPH/EPHRIN* and *CXCR4* signalling [137]. Furthermore, the optic vesicle seems to be influenced by both dorsal and ventral organizers, displaying the control the telencephalic *FOXG1* and hypothalamic *FOXD1*, both mutual repressors and controlled by dorsal *FGFs* and ventral *SHH*, respectively [138].

There remains one question, is it possible to segment the secondary prosencephalon antero-posteriorly as a whole? The prosomeric model by Puelles [90; 139] suggests an anterior prosomere, the *hypothalamus terminalis*, and a more posterior prosomere, the *hypothalamus peduncularis*. The ANR would induce the *hypothalamus terminalis* that will derive into the optic vesicle, preoptic area and all hypothalamic nuclei from the anterior commissure up to the division of mammilar and retrommamar nuclei [140; 141]. On the other hand, the *hypothalamus peduncularis* would receive posteriorizing signals that will lead to the alar telencephalon evagination and define posterior hypothalamic nuclei [90]. The acroterminal organizer is a secondary organizer rostral to the diencephalic floor plate that plays an important role in the hypothalamus subdivision [140], but there is no consensus about the morphogenic mechanism or its final outcome.

Finally, there are many other transcription factors involved in this anteroposterior subdivision such as the *FEZF* family, *BHLH* family, *LIM* family, etc. The early cell types of the prosencephalon are not as clearly defined as in the rhombencephalon. Nonetheless, the appearance of single cell technologies

has opened the doors to further studying prosencephalic patterning [142; 143; 144; 125; 145] and we expect to further define these IRNs in the next coming decades.

The evolutionary origin of the vertebrate brain bauplan

Although these IRNs might be highly conserved across bilaterians, recent studies of patterning in other chordates have identified likely subtle differences in the segmentation of their early brain. Below we will review these similarities and differences for cephalochordates and urochordates:

As discussed at the beginning of this chapter, the anteroposterior patterning is extremely conserved in bilaterians [21; 97], and the cephalochordates are not an exception. These chordates display a *HOX* segmented hindbrain, rostral *AmphiPax6* expression and other vertebrate known markers [146; 147].

Nonetheless, the model proposed by Albuixech-Crespo et al. (2017) [11] is much simpler than the vertebrate bauplan, and divides the early brain into three regions: an anterior hypothalamic area, a joint diencephalic-mesencephalic area and a posterior rhombencephalon. Although it could be hypothesised that the midbrain and evaginated telencephalon are vertebrate innovations [11; 148], the adult amphioxus displays a more complex patterning in the adult with *FOXG1* and *EMX2* expression in the prospective telencephalon [149]. There seems not to be a consensus about the isthmus existence. Although *AmphiEN* is expressed suggesting the presence of an isthmus, this gene is expressed later than expected for an embryonic organizer [11]. Thus, although the anteroposterior IRNs seem to be ancestral to vertebrates [150], there is not enough developmental evidence to unravel the mechanism of the adult telencephalon dorsalization in contrast with the rather hypothalamic features of amphioxus larvae.

Equivalently, urochordates also display shared antero-posterior features (*SIX3*, *PITX*, *OTX*, *EN*, *HOX* genes, among others) as well as a dorso-ventral gradient of *BMPs* and *HH*, as reviewed by [151]. All in all, there seems that IRNs are highly conserved across chordates despite the discussed neurulation and patterning differences. Although diversity of regions size or proliferation during this patterning might have had an important effect, it is likely that later developmental programs were more essential to conform the vertebrate lineage as we know it.

3. The mechanisms of diversification, divergent programs of neural development

To understand how later divergence is created, we must understand the mechanisms behind a high conserved structure such as the phylotypic brain. Although there are many hypotheses to justify the conservation of the phylotypic stages (reviewed in [152]), pleiotropy is considered the main responsible feature for this major developmental constraint of the middle stages versus earlier and later ones [16; 153; 154]. As described in the previous section, the middle stages IRNs are in charge of the patterning and positional information. These IRNs are highly multifunctional, being employed in several organs and developmental timepoints. If the mutation of an IRN affects multiple organs and processes, it will likely result in lethal consequences. Thus, the probability of evolution is very limited [155].

However, when the brain bauplan is established, each vertebrate taxon initiates a specific developmental program guiding the formation of the adult brain (**Fig. 5A**). This process varies in duration across species, and it is within these diverse developmental trajectories that evolution discovered a source of variation, fostering the intricate diversification of vertebrate brains: neuronal composition and innovation, structural size and organisation, and the intricate internal circuitry within these brains [156].

Apparently, this high diversity conflicts with the low evolvability of the phylotypic IRNs. Nevertheless, as shown in Fig. 5c., we suggest that a unique combination of IRNs does create evolvable modular functional GRNs. Although anteroposterior TFs (e.g., *HOXA1*) and dorsoventral TFs (e.g. *NKX2-1*) might be highly pleiotropic, their combination as combined regulatory element is unique to specific tissues or developmental timepoints, and thus fully evolvable. Thus, the innovation and loss of cis-regulatory elements for this unique TF combination would result in effector genes available for selection that will drive beneficial or detrimental phenotypes (**Fig. 5C**).

Moreover, depending on the tissue specificity of the effector genes, the pleiotropic constraint will be partially maintained. For this reason, the exit of the hourglass would be completed when the sub-regionalization of all brain regions is completed and much less pleiotropic genes such as CRNs (e.g., ECM compounds) and functional proteins (e.g., channels) are now highly expressed (**Fig. 5B**). Briefly, we would consider that the IRNs are also highly conserved, but they drive the expression of divergent CRNs, which would be replaced by pleiotropic patterning IRNs on the phylotypic stage.

To recapitulate, the release from the phylotypic constraints leads to species-specific developmental programs that comprise these modular late functional GRNs. In the following section, we will summarise these sources of diversity, spanning from the genesis of neurons to the intricate maturation

of neuronal circuits. Our focus will be on exploring the diverse variations within these programs that have driven the process of brain diversification.

Figure 5.

Changes in the timing of neurogenesis

The initial developmental process leading to divergence is neurogenesis, wherein neural stem cells exhibit the proliferative capacity to generate postmitotic neurons. During the developmental phase when the neural tube takes form and undergoes patterning, all neural cells within the tube epithelium are initially neuroepithelial stem cells. Subsequently, a genetic switch occurs, transitioning their proliferative behaviour from primarily self-renewal to neurogenic activity [157]. This marks the commencement of neuronal generation within the brain. Although it is still unknown how conserved it is their transcriptomic identity, the fundamental program of neurogenesis remains conserved across vertebrates [158]. In accordance with this program, the first neurons emerge and differentiate in the spinal cord, followed by rhombencephalic and mesencephalic neurons dedicated to the nuclei associated with cranial nerves [159]. Additional early neuronal populations undergoing conserved developmental neurogenesis are located at the boundary between the preteum and mesencephalon, as well as in the hypothalamus [160].

In the scope of the limited investigations spanning various species, many aspects of neurogenesis seem broadly conserved across different vertebrate lineages [158; 161; 162]. However, despite the conservation of a fundamental plan, minor variations in neurogenesis have profound consequences for brain structure and function due to its significant influence on neuronal numbers. The remarkable diversity in neuronal numbers across species is particularly striking, ranging from several thousand neurons to many billions in large mammals [163; 164]. This wide range is primarily attributed to alterations that directly affect neurogenesis, such as temporal characteristics of neurogenesis or the relative rates of neurogenesis in specific brain regions compared to others [165].

In the realm of temporal features governing neurogenesis, two pivotal aspects significantly influence brain evolution, and these factors are closely intertwined. The first crucial aspect is the cell cycle length, an inherent property specific to each species [166]. The duration of the cell cycle exhibits considerable variation among species, characterized by rapid cycles in fish species and notably slower cycles in amniotes [167]. Even among amniotes, a broad spectrum exists, with gecko neural stem cells demonstrating a slow 50-hour cell cycle [168], while mouse neural stem cells, on average, feature a faster cycle of around 20 hours [169]. Another factor to consider is the variability of cell cycle length

within a particular species. For instance, mouse neural stem cells extend their cell cycle during embryonic neurogenesis, transitioning from a 12-hour cycle to a much lengthier 24-hour cycle at the conclusion of neurogenesis [170]. Similarly, primates experience a deceleration of the cell cycle during development but undergo acceleration in the later stages of neurogenesis [171; 172]. These interspecies or intraspecies variations in cell cycle length can result in the underproduction or overproduction of specific neuronal cell types at a given timepoint. A striking example is the generation of upper-layer cortical neurons in primates and carnivores, significantly expanded primarily due to an accelerated cell cycle enabling increased neuron production [173].

Another temporal factor influencing neurogenesis is the duration of the neurogenic period, exhibiting a wide range from mere hours or a couple of days in fish species to the significantly prolonged neurogenesis period observed in large mammals, spanning months [174; 175]. Alongside variations in the cell cycle, the timing of neurogenesis plays a pivotal role in shaping the diverse brains of vertebrates. An illustrative instance is found in the cerebellum of large mammals, particularly elephants. While neurogenesis is a highly conserved process in the cerebellum [161], the elephant's cerebellum experiences an exceptionally extended neurogenic period, resulting in a substantial evolutionary impact. The neurogenesis of granule cells, in particular, is remarkably prolonged. This prolonged neurogenesis has led to a massive production of granule cells, surpassing that of any other neuronal population. Consequently, granule cells constitute the largest population of a neuronal type in the entire animal kingdom, and the cerebellum of the elephant contains approximately 97% of all neurons in the elephant brain [176], which is one of the most densely populated brains.

Progenitors cell types and niche CRNs innovation

Neurogenesis, as previously highlighted, is regulated not only by temporal factors but also by diverse neural stem cell types. Radial glial cells (RGCs) stand out as the primary neural stem cell type, predominantly engaging in direct neurogenesis to generate neurons [157]. Nevertheless, in specific brain regions and developmental stages, alternative progenitors emerge, falling under the broader category of intermediate precursor cells [177; 178; 179]. These cells enhance the neurogenic capacity of a given brain area through indirect neurogenesis. Evolution has dynamically shaped the balance between direct and indirect neurogenesis across various vertebrate lineages and brain regions [180]. The presence of intermediate precursor cells introduces an additional dimension of variation into the evolutionary dynamics of brain development. Significantly, these cells may have played a crucial role in the evolutionary emergence and expansion of the mammalian neocortex [181]. However, the

existence of intermediate precursors in non-mammalian species, their homology and the shared expression of some key transcription factors are still a matter of debate.

Neuronal migration

The second fundamental aspect of brain development is neuronal migration. Neurons originate in the germinative zones of the neuroepithelium and undergo a crucial journey to reach their designated mantle zone regions, where they will eventually settle, differentiate, and assume functional roles. The manner in which neurons migrate directly influences the formation of distinct brain areas, thus exerting a profound impact on the evolutionary trajectory of the brain (refer to [182] for an in-depth review).

The migration movements are well studied in mammals but much less is known in other species. The main two types of neuronal movement, according to how the neuron moves in relation to the axis of the neural tube, are radial and tangential migrations. The process of radial migration in brain development involves the movement of cells from the ventricular lumen to the external portion of the neural tube. This migration is facilitated by RGCs, which play a crucial role in both the proliferation and guidance of neurons [183; 184]. Locally born neurons share a genetic signature inherited from their germinative zone, influencing their differentiation pathways [185]. The impact of radial migration varies across vertebrates, with amniote brains, particularly in mammals and birds, exhibiting a higher degree of radial migration than non-amniote brains [182]. In laminar brains, characterized by limited radial migration, neurons remain near the ventricular surface, resulting in simpler anatomical structures and less complex neuronal circuitry [186; 156]. Elaborated brains, on the other hand, show a complex distribution of neurons away from the periventricular region, leading to increased neuronal numbers and the formation of secondary structures such as cortical layers or nuclei [187]. As such, the structural products of radial migration contribute to highly populated brains with diverse connectivity, enabling elaborate brain species to adapt and succeed in various environments. And accordingly, the evolution of radial migration has played a crucial role in shaping the complexity and functional capabilities of vertebrate brains.

Tangential migration also played a significant role in brain evolution. Tangential migration is the process in which cells move tangentially to the radial axis of the neural tube. Neurons move from their birthplace to a different brain segment of morphogenic unit [188]. As opposed to neurons migrating radially, those undergoing tangential migration, carry a distinct genetic signature from their original environment, resulting in their differentiation into a new cellular type [189; 190]. This process occurs

throughout the central nervous system, influencing the development of various brain regions. Accordingly, the arrival of tangential neurons boosts neuronal diversity in the region they migrate in, and this directly correlates with complexification of brain during evolution [182]. Tangential migration has been observed for many different neuronal types, including glutamatergic, GABAergic or aminergic neuronal populations. Importantly, this migration led to the emergence of diverse interneuronal cell types.

The impact of tangential migration on brain morphology and physiology varies among vertebrate groups, with elaborated brains largely shaped by this process. The promotion of new cellular types through tangential migration contributes to evolutionary diversity and complexity in brain networks, highlighting its crucial role in brain evolution. There are very relevant examples of cells that migrate differentially in vertebrate taxa. For instance, pallial glutamatergic cells are known to migrate within the pallium of mammals, following diverse neuronal routes [191; 192]. However, these migrations were not found in the pallium of birds [193; 194]. Because of the developmental role of these glutamatergic neurons, their lack of migration in birds directly implies novelties in mammals. Other example are cortical GABAergic interneurons of the human cortex, which are known to migrate towards the prefrontal cortex in a human-specific extended period of corticogenesis [195].

Tangential migration is a widespread phenomenon observed across various brain regions and species [182]. One notable example is the locus coeruleus in the brainstem, where noradrenergic neurons undergo ventralwards tangential migration from the alar region of rhombomere 1 to their final position in the basal plate of r1, playing crucial roles in homeostatic control [196]. Tangential migrations originating from the rhombic lip in the brainstem contribute to the diversification of neuronal types in structures like the pontine nuclei, inferior olive, reticular nuclei, and cuneatus nucleus, influencing early vertebrate brainstem evolution [197]. In the olfactory system, pallial interneurons migrate tangentially from the subpallium to the olfactory bulb, supporting continuous circuit formation throughout an animal's life [198].

Moreover, tangential migration plays a key role in the cerebellum, particularly in the migration of GABAergic granule cells, as introduced above. Unlike locally born Purkinje cells, granule cells undergo tangential migration from the rhombic lip to the external granule cell layer, contributing to the massive population of granule cells in the adult cerebellum [199]. This form of migration varies across vertebrates, with tetrapods exhibiting external migration and birds and mammals displaying migration at a premitotic state [200; 201]. Tangential migration not only increases neuronal numbers but also modifies internal connectivity within cerebellar circuits, bringing together granule cells and Purkinje

cells, impacting the efficiency of cerebellar processing circuits. These examples underscore the diverse roles of tangential migration in shaping brain architecture and function during development and evolution.

Cell type innovation

Another crucial factor promoting brain diversification was the variable programs of differentiation of neurons. This differentiation is influenced by both intrinsic factors, such as the neurogenic time of birth, and the extrinsic microenvironment. Likely the area of the brain that has received a major attention in this regard is the pallium, in the dorsal secondary prosencephalon. Major types of pallial neurons, including glutamatergic and pallial interneurons, are conserved across amniote species [202; 203; 204; 205; 206]. The expression of central transcription factors like *FOXP1*, *PAX6*, *TBR1*, *RORB*, *SATB2*, and *CTIP2* is shared among these neurons. Single-cell RNA sequencing has further revealed the existence of broad cortical pyramidal neurons in reptiles, suggesting a conserved mechanism initiating the program of glutamatergic neuronal differentiation in all amniotes [204; 202]. However, beyond the main neuronal types, diverse subtypes have evolved, with dozens of subtypes described in some lineages [202; 203; 204; 205]. Evolutionary tinkering, driven by intrinsic genomic and extrinsic environmental factors, led to the diversification of pallial neurons. In mammals, the complexity of neuronal subtypes is being revealed with advancements in single-cell RNA technology [142; 143; 144; 125; 145; 207], whereas reptilian neurons do not exhibit the same level of diversification. For instance, sauropsid neurons lack the variety of combinatorial transcription factor codes found in mammalian neurons, contributing to their relative simplicity [208].

In the case of lampreys, glutamatergic neurons of the pallium seem similar to those of mammals only at the major cell type level, but not at a specific cell type level [206]. This holds also true for the amphibian pallium, which showed similarities of some glutamatergic neurons but not for the glutamatergic cortical neurons [205; 209]. And, although more complex of a comparison, as well for avian and non-avian reptiles [203]. These broad similarities accompanied by specific differences are the product of differential programs of neuronal maturation. Mammalian pallial neurons have undergone a spectacular case of neuronal diversification of neuronal types, all enabled by a parallel diversification of their brains and functionally-related neuronal populations. At molecular level, it is being a challenge to identify the novel mechanisms enabling this diversification or co-option of expression modules. Differences in the regulation of genes, such as *SATB2* and *CTIP2*, underlie the diversity of sauropsid pallial neurons [208].

On the other hand, the GABAergic population used to be highly conserved cell types across vertebrates. As explained before, this cell type is produced in the subpallium across all vertebrate species [210; 211; 212; 213; 193] , including humans, and then migrates tangentially to the pallium during development. However, recent findings demonstrate that the human neocortex, particularly the mammalian neocortex with the highest neuron count, also produces GABAergic interneurons locally within the dorsal pallium [214; 215]. This unique aspect of human pallial progenitors developmental program sets it apart from other mammalian species and might contribute significantly to the diversification of cortical interneurons. It urges the question whether this particular feature is also shared with other primates, or even other mammals.

Innovation on the GRNs also impact the efferent connectivity of each neuronal type, as observed in marsupials. Birds, particularly parrots and corvids, may have neuronal complexity comparable to primates, but a thorough comparison and understanding of avian pallial neurons await further single-cell RNA studies.

Neuronal circuits

Ultimately, the paramount factor propelling brain evolution is the consolidation of neuronal circuits. The developmental program of a neuron type, encompassing its neurogenesis, migration, and differentiation plans, dictates the neuron's communication with specific targets in the brain. However, as a consequence of shifts in these developmental programs, neurons in one species may establish connections with different targets than their homologous counterparts in another species. This alteration in neuronal communication can wield a profound influence on the functional and even behavioral aspects of vertebrate brains, potentially underpinning the numerous species-specific signatures of neuronal connectivity observed across diverse species [216; 217].

A notable instance is found in the visual pathway of tetrapods. Initially, in amphibian brains, the primary destination for most visual information from retinal neurons lies in the prethalamus [156]. Over the course of evolution, this central target has undergone significant shifts: towards the thalamus in reptiles and predominantly to the thalamus in birds and mammals [218]. In the parallel collothalamic pathway, visual information is first relayed in the sensorial alar mesencephalon. This parallel pathway experiences a substantial increase in importance in reptiles and birds, with its ultimate target in the pallium also expanding significantly [219]. In mammals, on the contrary, the collothalamic pathway holds less significance, and the main pallial area receiving lemnothalamic information is both more diverse and expanded. However, the developmental cues governing the emergence and enhancement

of novel communication pathways, or those influencing the balance of parallel pathways towards one or the other, remain largely unknown.

Recently, a novel developmental scenario has been proposed for explaining these novel communications. In the case of the deep cerebellar nuclei, it has been proposed that the nuclear evolution followed a duplication and divergence scenario [220]. The authors delved into the evolution of brain regions at the level of cell types in the cerebellar nuclei, which are the output structures of the cerebellum. Through the use of single-nucleus RNA sequencing in mice, chickens, and humans, along with comprehensive tracing of projections throughout the central nervous system, a conserved set of cell types was identified. This set includes two excitatory neuron classes specific to particular regions and three inhibitory neuron classes invariant across regions. The neuronal set represents a foundational cerebellar nucleus that underwent repetitive duplications during evolution to give rise to new regions. In amniote evolution, the nucleus comprising this set of cells was duplicated, and because its function was reiterative, it was allowed its functional divergence and specification. This example of duplication of divergence may have been common in brain evolution.

Conclusion

In essence, starting from the early stages of the neural tube, each vertebrate brain embarks on crafting a distinct organ characterized by myriad singularities and species-specific traits. In terms of cell types, functions, and gene expression, the vertebrate brain stands out as the most diverse organ in the natural world. Yet, beneath this rich tapestry of distinctions, a common bauplan persists, preserved in evolution for approximately 500 million years. Remarkably, this shared bauplan not only orchestrates the developmental principles governing the creation of various brain forms but also imposes constraints that regulate the diversity of brains.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Author Contributions

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Figure Legends

Figure 1. The hourglass model: Evolutionary developmental diversity at a glance. **A.** The whole embryo hourglass. Early stages at the bottom, late ones at the top, intermediate or phylotypic at the middle. Inside, representative cartoons for each stage and different vertebrate species. **B.** The brain hourglass. As in *a*, earlier stages (neurulation) are at the bottom, later ones (neurogenesis) are at the top and intermediates (patterning) are at the middle part. Cartoons representative of each stage and brain species are indicated inside and a belt indicates the evolutionary constraints. **C.** Deuterostome evolutionary tree. Evolutionary relationships among different deuterostome clades, with the indication of subgroups such as chordates, vertebrates, and amniotes.

Fig. 2. The bottleneck of the hourglass. **A,B.** IRNs in gastrulation and early neurulation. Sequential scheme of gastrulation (a) and early neurulation (b) with the tissues (Dark blue, neuroectoderm (NE); light blue, non-neural ectoderm (NNE); yellow, mesoderm (M); red, endoderm (E); orange, Spemann-Mangold organiser (SMO)) and morphogens (green, *BMPs*; orange, *CHORDIN*; purple; *CERBERUS (CB)*; yellow, *SHH*). While A represents the gastrulation *CHORDIN-BMPs* gradient, B show the anteroposterior gradient of *CERBERUS* vs *WNTs* and the dorsoventral *BMPs-SHH*. Although this cartoon represents amphibian gastrulation, these IRNs can be identified in the rest of vertebrates. **C-E.** Geometries of late gastrulation (c), early (d) and late (e) neurulation across vertebrates. **C.** Late gastrulation is characterised by the following summarised processes: mesodermal migration and neuroectoderm anterior extension. The prechordal plate (PCP) or anterior ventral endoderm (AVE) (purple) protects the anterior neuroectoderm from other morphogens expressing *CB* and other molecules (B'). The notochord forms and induces the future ventral neuroectoderm via *SHH* (B''). These processes share IRNs, but need different CRNs to achieve the final equivalent neural tube (NT). **D.** Early neurulation is different across vertebrates: Mouse and chicken display a pseudoepithelial neuroectoderm, amphibians two layers (superficial and deep) and zebrafish a disorganised neural keel. **E.** Late neurulation is quite diverse in amniotes, displaying different hinge points for neurulation and proliferation rates dorsoventrally. Amphibians neural tube is quite engrossed and multi-layered and the non-neural neuroectoderm rapidly epibolies. Zebrafish non-neural ectoderm epibolies the

neural keel from the beginning. The initial disorganised neural keel forms a lumen by radial intercalation. Abbreviations: A, anterior; D, dorsal; P, posterior; V, ventral.

Fig. 3. The origins of the vertebrate neurulating brain. **A.** The IRNs of a CNS. The first cartoon summarises the experiments carried out in Su et al, 2019 (control gastrulating indirect developer hemichordate, when added *BMP* in the media and the fate map of a vertebrate (frog)). In control, the left side is the ventral ectoderm, which is divided in an inner ventral non-neural ectoderm (VE) and the outer neural ciliary band (NE). When the *BMP* is abundant in the media, the ciliary band internalises and locates underneath the ventral ectoderm (A''). This is similar to the neural invagination caused by the epiboly of the *BMP*-secreting non-neural ectoderm (A'''). Moreover, the mouth at the high chordin side disappears in +*BMP* conditions, so it would probably cause the appearance of a *BMP* side mouth as in vertebrates (A'''). **B.** Primitive neurulation. This cartoon summarises the neurulation of the collar cord of hemichordates as well as the dorso-ventral patterning induced by the stomochord and the non-neural ectoderm, likely homologue to chordates. **C.** The limits of the neural tube across vertebrates. This figure displays the differences across vertebrates regarding anterior neuropore (NP). This NP remains open in cephalochordates and urochordates, but the latter group reuses it as a mouth, connecting endoderm and ectoderm (hypophyseal-hypothalamus). Although the anterior neuropore does close in vertebrates, this most anterior region is also controlled by *PITX* network. In contrast with cephalochordates, where *PITX* network controls only the mouth (no neural). This *PITX* region is the hypophysis-hypothalamus connection, also known as Rathke's pouch in development.

Fig. 4. The regionalization of the nervous system. **A.** The morphogens of the phylotypic brain IRNs. **B.** The segmentation or developmental cell types of the phylotypic vertebrate brain. **C,D.** The dorso-ventral (c) and antero-posterior (d) patterning IRNs (mainly transcription factors expression) of the phylotypic vertebrate brain. Abbreviations: a, alar; A, Anterior; ab, alarbasal (intermediate); ANR, Anterior Neural Ridge; ATO; Acroterminal Organizer; b, basal; D, Dorsal; DIEN, diencephalon; FP, floor plate; HB, hindbrain (rhombomere); HEM, Cortical Hem; IT, isthmus; MB, midbrain (mesencephalon); P, posterior; P1-3, prosomeres 1-3; PAL, pallium; pHt, peduncular hypothalamus; RP, roof plate; SPAL, subpallium; tHt, terminal hypothalamus; V, ventral; ZLI, zona limitans Intrathalamica.

Fig. 5. The hourglass model: The mechanisms that constraint neural diversity. **A.** Brain Evo-Devo Diversity. Summary of the main process corresponding to each stage. **B.** The percentage of the

transcriptome related to developmental processes: Environment and maternal CRGs process, pleiotropic patterning IRNs, and functional GRNs. These different processes are majoritarian of one stage, but they also overlap during development. **C.** Hypothesized model for GRNs evolution across neural development. The same IRNs (represented with TFs) control divergent set of effector genes or CRNs that are responsible for early diversity. The CREs of common TFs are divergently located and the same transcription factor complex drives a different set of genes or CRNs. Also, these TFs also control later developmental IRNs that determine D-V and A-P patterning segments. The combination of these expressed TFs drives the unique expression of cell type or segment specific gene sets. However, as in early processes, this TFs complex drives different gene sets due to divergence in their CREs. The colour of the stuffing matches the developmental process and the line colour with the species (black common, green/gold species-specific).